

Supplementary Material on BizDev Communication

June 5, 2023

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This document is a supplementary material of the paper “Analyzing the BizDev Interface in an Enterprise Context: A Case of Developers Acting in Business” by Caique G Moreira, Breno B. N. de França, and Tayana U. Conte. Here, we describe categories supporting the main phenomena w.r.t. the BizDev communication. These categories form an axis around reasons for communication and two dimensions ranging from good to bad communication attributes and causes.

1 Attributes and causes of good BizDev communication

There was a frequent exchange of information between BizDev teams, enabling them to stay aligned during different stages of development. A strong characteristic of the BizDev communication observed at CompanyP was the presence of open communication, allowing information to be exchanged freely and quickly with no hierarchy hindrances. Even though we were able to identify several examples of good BizDev communication, this behavior is not present at all times. In Section 2 we present opposite situations. In the following, we describe the main attributes and reasons for good BizDev communication (Figure 1).

High frequency of BizDev communication One main reason for this high frequency was the creation of “**core teams**”, which were multidisciplinary squads composed of people from Product, Design, and Development. The Content Leader reported a higher frequency of communication resulted in a higher level of alignment between different teams, preventing communication issues

Figure 1: Codes related to Good BizDev Communication

that happened in the past. When asked about what could have prevented some past conflicts between her/his team and the development team, s/he stated: *“More alignments, that’s for sure. More communication itself, teams talking more to each other.”* (P7). S/he concluded that a higher frequency of communication between the Content, Product, and Development team also helped reduce communication noises: *“And then I saw a large communication noise. (..) But today it is a lot better (...) And I think it is not only that we included more people in the communication, but that we communicated more. The Product Team, for example, did not have a weekly meeting with the Content team before. The Mobile (Development) team did not have this weekly meeting with the Product Team (..). So, I think the alignments did help; closer meetings; more constant meetings. Even though I hate a lot of meetings, (...), some of them are necessary.”* (P7).

Business people having technology knowledge Technology knowledge from business people contributes to good BizDev Communication as it gives business people a better understanding of the technical jargon developers and complexity of the requests made to the IT sector and technical limitations, also improving effort estimation.

One Mobile Developer (P6) reported s/he felt explaining technical problems to a former Product Manager was easier because of the manager’s technical knowledge. The Content leader reported that due to her/his acquired technical knowledge, s/he was able to question estimation efforts provided by the development team: *“And then s/he said that to develop that WebView it would take one and a half months. So I started looking at that estimation and asked why it would take so long. A WebView should not take one and a half months to be developed. (..) And then the developer said: ‘Actually there is another thing I need to do before the WebView, there is this other thing..’ So I got the issue was another thing.”* (P7).

Because of her/his technical knowledge, the Content Leader was able to perceive that part of the effort estimation given by the developer included prioritization of other tasks, and removing a communication noise that would affect the project's planning. : *“And then we can prioritize the project as well. Because if s/he tells me that it will take one and a half months and I don't understand it (the technical complexity), every time I need to update that (the WebView), I will insert one and a half months on my deadline.”* (P7). One of the Content Analysts also reported that technical knowledge allowed her/him to perceive technical restrictions before even reporting to the development team, reducing the need for unnecessary BizDev communication: *“So, if we already have it (technical knowledge), even before we bring it to the technology teams, we can realize that it may have implications. Because we will have this previous knowledge, right? And then we can decide sometimes not to raise a feature request because we know we would be wasting time if we did. Because it would not be a priority, or because it would not be that easy to implement.”* (P12).

There were cases in which business people had a previous technical background, as noticed by people from Product and Growth teams: *“So, yes, a good fraction of people from Growth and CRM teams have a technical background. (...) Generally speaking, in our team, we have statisticians, people who studied computer science and ended up changing to another area, and people that graduated in Mechatronics Engineering. (...) This proximity with technology turns out to make things easier, and overall it is not an obstacle. But this is something more related specifically to our team's profile.”* (P13).

Efforts to continuously improve BizDev communication These efforts were taken not only to increase the frequency of communication but also to make it clearer and more fluid.

Different developers (P1, P6, P9, P15) reported they would take special efforts to speak in a simpler way, avoiding technical jargon when possible and provide technical context when needed. The back-end developer reported: *“When I talk to people from other areas, I always keep in mind that those people are not used to many terms that I use, so I try to avoid technical jargon. However, in moments when I need to use them, I usually explain what the jargon means first, (...) And after that I start referring to the jargon assuming that the person knows it.”* (P15). Those efforts from technology teams were perceived by one Content Analyst: *“But I see a predisposition of the (Development) team to present this information for us (Content team) in a much clearer way, trying to level the information. (...). And to try to translate it to a language people from other teams will understand.”* (P12). Their motivations to improve communication come from leader incentives (P9) and also bad communication experiences (P15).

The hiring of the product manager (**P8**) was also perceived as an effort to improve BizDev Communication (reported by **P2**). Some of the changes s/he introduced were the centralization of all communication related to ProductP at a single Slack channel and the use of a common issue tracking system ([Monday](#)¹) to all teams working with ProductP, centralizing information about feature's requirements, progresses and deadlines.

Open communication at the BizDev interface We observed open communication between the IT and the business sector, indicating a transparent exchange of information without hierarchical or bureaucratic barriers. Developers could easily access people from Business to get clarification about requirements and present development progress.

Both the Growth Analyst (**P13**) and the Content Leader (**P3**) reported they observed all teams were open to receive questioning and suggestions about their work, having at the same time the freedom to reach other teams for the same reason. Both of them credited CompanyP's culture for this scenario. In particular, different interviewees (**P4, P11, P14, P15**) reported that the business area was and that it should always continue being, open for receiving business questioning from the technology area. The developers reported that people from the Product team were receptive to their business suggestions and questioning, and helped them validate their ideas for new requirements. The Product analyst stated that the ideal process for all project implementations would include a moment for people from technology areas to present their opinions.

An observed behavior also indicating open BizDev communication is that members from business teams did not feel they needed to channel communication through Technology leaders. This behavior was observed by several people both from business (**P3, P8, P12, P14**) and development (**P2, P11, P15**) areas. When asked about differences in the quality of BizDev communication between tech leaders and analysts, the product manager stated: *"In my conversations, I did not perceive much of that (difference). (...) I did not have difficulties in communicating with analysts regarding, for example, understanding product requirements, discussing, and being able to uplift the conversation in terms of not staying only at a technical level (...). So with all of them (IT people) I never had the issue of trying to connect the business requirement with the technological ones."* (**P8**).

¹Monday a work management platform, used by organizations to track projects and workflows, improving team collaboration: <https://monday.com/>

2 Attributes and causes of bad BizDev communication

Even though many interview segments pointed to the existence of good and healthy BizDev Communication at CompanyP, we were also able to identify attributes of bad BizDev Communication (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Codes related to Bad BizDev Communication

Business members lacking technology knowledge Different business (P7, P12) and technology (P6, P9) people reported that lack of technology knowledge by business members could harm the BizDev communication, mainly due to issues from the use of technical jargon, as stated by the Content Leader: “*It’s not even they don’t understand, but since there are words (technical jargon) they don’t use, they feel intimidated to give an answer (to tech teams). ‘I think I’m right, I think I understood. But I’m afraid to continue this conversation because I feel like I don’t know what I’m talking about’ (..) And then, they sometimes feel intimidated to even propose ideas. Because they don’t have that knowledge, they can’t speak the same jargon.*” (P7).

Two mobile developers (P6, P9) stated they would expend more time providing context and explaining technical details in cases when business people lacked technology knowledge, which led to slower BizDev communication.

Development analysts with poor communication skills Business members’ lack of technology knowledge is worsened in situations where development analysts have poor communication skills and are unable to communicate without the excessive use of technical jargon. Development analysts lacking communication skills also harm BizDev communication when these analysts feel frightened

to reach business people or when business people start to avoid communicating with these analysts, prioritizing communication with development leaders.

Communication noise and misalignment at BizDev communication

As mentioned previously, there were times when developers' use of technical jargon led to communication noises. The opposite behavior was also observed when the back-end developer communicated with the marketing team and business jargon was used: *"Now, I think that with the remainder of the Marketing team, the difficulty (that I have) with jargon is big. Because there are... I feel there are many acronyms, at many moments, and each acronym has a meaning, a context. So I think it's a lot to have in mind, and in their case (Marketing people), they already do. But sometimes when we need to communicate, we end up getting lost on our way to understanding each other."* (P15). Another reason for communication noises at the BizDev interface the back-end developer perceived was the lack of context when business people reach tech people assuming they already have the necessary business context for engaging in conversation.

Another cause of communication noises was the physical structure of CompanyP, in which some business Teams were located in different cities than the development teams, combined with a bad performance at asynchronous written communication. Several participants (P1, P2, P4, P5, P6, P9, P15) reported that, on CompanyP, the preference was to communicate in person or through audio calls, and some participants also stated one motivation for this preference was to avoid loss of information.

We concluded the physical separation of some business and development teams represented a relevant source of communication noises. The physical distance between some teams prevents communication in person from happening. Furthermore, development analysts tend to avoid audio conversations and the performance in written communication was poor, introducing communication noises and being slower than audio communication.

From different transcriptions, we observe misalignment between BizDev teams: *"We did not visualize what the other teams were working on, and who were the responsible ones, the responsible areas for every project."* (P12). Examples include two teams working on the idealization of a new feature for the project at the same time, and the announcement of a feature to the customers before being finished.

In order to alleviate those bad communication aspects some participants proposed improvement opportunities for the BizDev communication, summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Improvement Opportunities for the BizDev Communication

Improvement Opportunity	Participants
Increase frequency of BizDev communication	P12, P13
Diversify communication methods, documenting conversation and business decisions	P13, P15
Involve more business analysts on BizDev discussions	P12
IT people should abstract technical details	P8
Business area and tech leaders should provide more business context to tech analysts	P8
Translate strategic goals and KPIs into more applicable concepts	P8